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TECHNOLOGY****EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS ON THE EFFECT OF PROCESS PARAMETERS
DURING CNC TURNING ON NYLON -6/6 USING TUNGSTEN CARBIDE TOOL****Manas Ranjan Panda*, Swadhin Kumar Biswal and Yogesh Kumar Sharma**

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ABSTRACT

Quality and productivity of the machined parts are the main challenges of metal cutting industry during turning process. Therefore we should optimize and analyse the cutting parameters in such a way that the required surface quality can be controlled. Turning is the most widely material removal process in industrial area. It is important to study the effect of the cutting parameters on MRR and surface roughness to improve machinability. The purpose of this paper is to study the effect of speed, feed and depth of cut on surface roughness (Ra) and MRR in turning nylon-6/6 using tungsten carbide tool. Experiments were conducted on a CNC lathe and the influence of cutting parameters was studied using analysis of variance (ANOVA). Based on the main effects plots optimum level for surface roughness was chosen from the three levels of cutting parameters considered. From the experiment it is found that feed, depth of cut, and the interaction of feed and depth of cut significantly influenced the variance. We have calculated the main effects and percentage contribution of various process parameters affecting surface roughness also determined.

KEYWORDS: CNC Turning, Taguchi Orthogonal Array, Nylon-6/6, Surface Roughness (Ra), Tungsten Carbide tool

INTRODUCTION

A lathe is a machine tool which rotates the work piece on its axis to perform various operations like turning, cutting, knurling, drilling, or deformation, facing by the help of cutting tools which are applied to the work piece to create a symmetric object. The work piece is held horizontally to the lathe bed by the jaws. Other work-holding methods include clamping the work about the axis of rotation using a chuck and tool is held by the tool post which perform different operations on the work piece. Out of all material removing process turning is the most important operation. Turning is a material removal process which removes metal from cylindrical object and hence reduce its diameter in order to get a certain diameter object with good surface finish. The main objective is always to increase the productivity with lowest manufacturing cost.

Surface roughness produced on the work piece is an important property which plays major role in production. Surface roughness determines the quality of the production and the quality of the product. Roughness on surface of the object is undesirable but at the same time it is unavoidable. On the other hand in order to get good surface roughness the machining process expensive. So a proper combination of cutting parameters that is cutting speed, feed and depth of cut should be selected so that we can achieve good surface roughness in lowest possible cost.

TAGUCHI METHOD

Taguchi method is an optimization method which is powerful tool for the design of quality systems. It is a statistical method used which improves the quality of products. It has various application in industry as well as various research organisations. Taguchi method is a step by step approach for the optimization of design which increases

quality and performance and minimizes cost. It is an easy approach for optimization and don't need highly skilled users. The suitable input parameters for god surface roughness can be obtained by using Taguchi method.

Fig 1. Turning of nylon-6/6 in CNC lathe

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND CUTTING CONDITION

1. Work piece material

The work piece material is nylon-6/6 which is a thermoplastic polymer. It has good thermal and wear resistance, good strength and stiffness. It has wide range of application in textile, metal working, aircraft and material handling. Nylon is also used as a replacement for brass, wood rubber, aluminium and steel.

1. Process Variables

The process variables are cutting speed, feed and depth of cut. The experiment is conducted as per Taguchi's orthogonal array which has reduced the number of experiments. A range of the levels were identified for individual parameters with trial experiments as shown in Table 1.

2. Machining Process

The turning process was performed on a CNC lathe with tungsten carbide tool for its high thermal resistance and hardness. As per Taguchi L9 Orthogonal array, nine number of experiments were carried out as per Table 2 with its individual parameters and levels.

The Nylon 6/6 rod is cut into equal pieces of size 30 mm in diameter and 95 mm in length. Then the workpiece were fixed in the 3 jaw chuck of the CNC lathe and turning operation was performed for each job.

Table 1 Factors and their level

Level	Cutting speed (rpm)	Feed rate (mm/min)	Depth of cut (mm)
1	1000	0.1	0.1
2	1200	0.2	0.2
3	1400	0.3	0.3

Table 2 Orthogonal L9 array of Taguchi

Experiment no.	Cutting speed (rpm)	Feed rate (mm/min)	Depth of cut (mm)	Theoretical MRR (mm ³ /min)
1	1000	0.1	0.1	922.025
2	1000	0.2	0.2	3688.229
3	1000	0.3	0.3	8298.517
4	1200	0.1	0.2	2212.937
5	1200	0.2	0.3	6638.813
6	1200	0.3	0.1	3319.406
7	1400	0.1	0.3	3872.641
8	1400	0.2	0.1	2581.760
9	1400	0.3	0.2	7745.282

ANALYSIS OF SURFACE ROUGHNESS

The following table shows the value of surface roughness obtained from the experiment at different level of cutting parameters.

Fig 2. Machined specimens and Surface roughness test of nylon-6/6

Table 3 Surface roughness readings

<i>Expt. Run</i>	<i>Cutting Speed (RPM)</i>	<i>Feed (mm/min)</i>	<i>Depth of Cut (mm)</i>	<i>Surface Roughness (μm)</i>
1	1000	0.1	0.1	4.580
2	1000	0.2	0.2	5.960
3	1000	0.3	0.3	7.041
4	1200	0.1	0.2	4.267
5	1200	0.2	0.3	4.350
6	1200	0.3	0.1	6.231
7	1400	0.1	0.3	2.228
8	1400	0.2	0.1	3.435
9	1400	0.3	0.2	4.743

Analysis of variance for surface roughness

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) consist of statistical models which analyse the difference among means and its associate procedures. The following table gives the ANOVA with F-value and P-values and percentage contribution. The most significant factor is cutting speed and feed that contribute to the surface roughness and depth of cut has very less contribution on surface roughness.

Table 4 Analysis of variance for means R-sq = 98.8% R-sq(adj) = 95.48%

Source	DF	Seq SS	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P	% contribution
Cutting speed	2	8.7424	8.7424	4.3712	43.56	0.022	50.1938
Feed	2	8.1695	8.1695	4.0847	40.70	0.024	46.9045
Depth of cut	2	0.3047	0.3047	0.1524	1.52	0.397	1.7494
Residual error	2	0.2007	0.2007	0.1004			1.1523
Total	8	17.4173					

Response optimizer

Response optimizer is used to optimize the surface roughness and to the desired ranking for all the process parameters according to its Delta value.

Table5. Response table for means

Level	Cutting speed	Feed	Depth of cut
1	5.860	3.692	4.749
2	4.949	4.582	4.990
3	3.469	6.005	4.540
Delta	2.392	2.313	0.450
Rank	1	2	3

MAIN EFFECTS PLOT

Main effects plots for this experiment as shown in Fig. 3 tells that, when cutting speed increases surface roughness (Ra) decreases, when depth of cut increases surface roughness first increases then decreases but when feed increases surface roughness (Ra) increases. As surface roughness fulfils the smaller the better criteria, so the optimum points for process parameters are, Cutting speed 1400 rpm, Feed 0.1 mm/min and Depth of cut 0.3 mm.

Fig. 3 Main effect plot for Surface Roughness

CONCLUSION

- Surface roughness is mainly influenced by cutting speed and feed rate and depth of cut has insignificant role.
- From the above experiment it is found that surface roughness decreases with increase in cutting speed whereas surface roughness increases with increase in feed rate.
- As surface roughness fulfils the smaller the better criteria, so the optimum points for process parameters are, Cutting speed 1400 rpm, Feed 0.1 mm/min and Depth of cut 0.3 mm.

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